

A Progression-Style Thermal-Hydraulic Benchmark for Molten Salt Reactor Modeling Using SyTH

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a suite of thermal-hydraulic progression problems developed to support the advancement of modeling capabilities for molten salt reactors (MSRs). This work is based on the operating conditions and design characteristics of the Molten Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE). The progression problems are structured to perform system-level simulations using the System Thermal-Hydraulic (SyTH) code through a variety of steady-state single-phase and two-phase molten-salt flow cases with conjugate heat transfer between the salt and graphite.

The simplest case begins with a single-channel forced-flow problem with no heat sources. The subsequent cases introduce additional physics by applying uniform and non-uniform heat-generation profiles to the salt and graphite. Further variations include adding void, adjusting the inlet flow rate, and modifying the salt composition. These problems are designed to assess the solvers used in SyTH and establish a thermal-hydraulic benchmark for a single channel.

A mesh-convergence study was first performed in SyTH, and the converged solutions were compared against the System Analysis Module (SAM). The code-to-code comparison shows suitable agreement within 0.62 K of the predicted salt temperature distributions for the single-phase fuel-salt cases under both uniform and non-uniform volumetric heat-source conditions. Overall, this work demonstrates a progression-style thermal-hydraulic benchmark for molten-salt systems using SyTH.

Keywords: Molten-Salt Reactors, Thermal-hydraulics, Multiphysics Modeling, MSRE

1. INTRODUCTION

Molten salt reactors (MSRs) represent one of the leading advanced reactor designs under development for the next generation of nuclear reactor power. Compared to traditional light water reactors (LWRs), MSRs offer performance and safety advantages including operating at high temperatures with relatively low pressure, increased thermal efficiency, fuel utilization, and online waste management [1]. These advantages stem from the unique characteristics of molten salts, which serves simultaneously as a coolant and fuel carrier. However, the distinct thermophysical properties, multiphase behavior, heat transfer, and reactivity feedback in liquid-fueled molten salts introduce new modeling and operational challenges that differ from conventional water-based solid-fuel reactor systems [2].

The Molten-Salt Reactor Experiment (MSRE) at Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) demonstrated the feasibility of liquid-fueled reactor operation while revealing key technical challenges [3,4]. During operation, helium gas was sparged into the fuel salt to remove gaseous fission products. A portion of this sparging gas became entrained within the flowing salt, which recirculated throughout the reactor. This entrainment introduced compressibility effects in the fuel density, which in turn caused fluctuations in reactivity and reactor power. Although the MSRE maintained power stability at relatively

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low thermal power, the behavior of high-power molten salt reactors under similar conditions remains uncertain. This underscores the need to model two-phase flow in addition to conjugate heat transfer (CHT) for MSRs.

This paper presents a progression-style suite of steady-state MSRE thermal-hydraulic benchmark cases, intended as a thermal-hydraulic counterpart to the neutronics progression problems in [5]. The cases are simulated with the System Thermal-Hydraulic (SyTH) code [6,7]. SyTH is a one-dimensional finite-volume thermal-hydraulics solver for salt-gas flow that includes CHT and volumetric heating in the salt and graphite. Single-phase simulations solve the mass-momentum and enthalpy conversation equations with standard wall-friction and heat-transfer closures across laminar to turbulent regimes, and two-phase flow is modeled using a simplified drift-flux formulation similar to [8].

The progression problems are first specified in terms of geometry, operating conditions, and simplifying assumptions. A mesh convergence study is then used to establish a converged discretization, after which SyTH predictions are benchmarked against the System Analysis Module (SAM), a verified and validated system-level code for advanced non-light-water reactor safety analysis [9]. Finally, the case-to-case progression results are analyzed and discussed to highlight physical trends between cases.

2. PROGRESSION PROBLEMS FOR MOLTEN SALT REACTOR MODELING

Progression problems provide a method for developing and demonstrating modeling capabilities for advanced reactor design and safety analysis. The structure of the approach is similar to the VERA Core Physics Benchmark Problems which defines a series of benchmark problems, each designed to progressively test specific aspects of individual or coupled physics [10].

Reference solutions are defined to enable quantitative comparison between different modeling tools and methods. The outputs to be compared are in the following: field solutions (e.g., temperature, velocity, pressure, and void fraction distributions), simulated sensor responses (e.g., pressure and flow gauge, thermocouples readings, and in-core/ex-core neutron flux detector), and integral quantities (average temperatures, criticality and reactivity, and thermal reactor power) for model verification and code-to-code comparisons.

The benchmark suite is intended to be applicable across multiphysics phenomena, including CHT, single-phase, and two-phase flow simulations. Each progression problem isolates and tests specific physical features relevant to molten salt reactor operation and builds up to multiphysics scenarios. The benchmark problems presented here are based on MSRE reports [3, 11] and published benchmarks [12, 13]. However, several modifications have been made to simplify the problem definitions for a clear and concise benchmark.

2.1. Single-channel Setup

For the single-channel configuration, an inlet temperature of 900.0 K and an outlet pressure of 0.149616 MPa were used, and the inlet volumetric flow rate was set to $6.31 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ using the approximation reported in [13]. The MSRE fuel salt was composed primarily of LiF, BeF₂, ZrF₄, and UF₄, with trace amounts of Cr, Fe, and Ni [14]. Although multiple correlations exist in the literature for molten salt density and other relevant thermophysical properties, this work focuses on two representative temperature-dependent correlations. The first thermophysical property correlations are based on pure FLiBe in [15], while a second evaluation is based on the approximated MSRE fuel salt properties reported in [14]. Lastly, helium void fractions under normal operating conditions were estimated to be 0.023-0.045% and less than 0.1% from pressure and neutron noise measurements [4, 16]. 2-3% void fraction could be artificially induced in experiments through abnormally low pump-bowl salt level [17]. For simplicity, the inlet void fraction was fixed at 1%, and helium was treated as incompressible with constant density, neglecting temperature-dependent density variations. Table I summarizes the single-channel specifi-

cations, while Figure 1 shows the uniform and axially varying volumetric heat sources applied in the benchmark.

Table I. Specifications for single-channel simulation input parameters.

Specification	Symbol / Variable	Type / Value
Channel Geometry		
Cross-section shape	–	Stadium
Cross-sectional area	A_c	2.875244 cm ²
Hydraulic diameter	D_h	1.58506 cm
Height	H	170.027 cm
Fluid and Solid Components		
MSRE fuel salt	LiF-BeF ₂ -ZrF ₄ -UF ₄	64.1-30.0-5.0-0.809 mol%
Pure salt	LiF-BeF ₂	67.0-33.0 mol%
Entrained gas	He	Helium
Moderator	C	Graphite
Boundary Conditions		
Inlet temperature	T_{in}	900.0 K
Inlet volumetric flow rate	Q_{in}	6.31×10^{-5} m ³ /s
Inlet void fraction	α_{in}	1.0% Helium
Outlet pressure	P_{out}	0.1496162 MPa
Uniform Heat Sources		
Graphite heat source	q'''_{solid}	0.5 W/cc
Fuel heat source	q'''_{liquid}	10.0 W/cc
Non-uniform Heat Sources		
Graphite heat source (axial)	$q'''_{solid}(z)$	$0.7163 \cos(0.0153z - 1.2677) + 0.0127$ W/cc
Fuel heat source (axial)	$q'''_{liquid}(z)$	$10.162 \sin\left(\pi \frac{z+11.07}{197.36}\right)$ W/cc

Figure 1. Uniform and axially varying volumetric heat sources prescribed in the salt and graphite.

Table II presents the single-channel progression problems designed to illustrate the gradual increase in complexity.

- Cases 1–2 begin with forced-flow without any heat generation in the solid or liquid regions;
- Cases 3–5 introduce uniform heating individually and then combined non-uniform heating for both the graphite and salt;
- Cases 6–8 build upon cases 3–5 by introducing void fraction; and
- Cases 9–11 and 12–14 apply uniform heat generation in the graphite while progressively increasing the inlet flow rate, first without voids and then with voids.

Table II. Progression Problem TH-1: Single-channel Progression Summary

Case Number	Flow Regime	Heating Condition	Void Fraction	Volumetric Flow Rate
1	Single-phase	–	–	Q_{in}
2	Two-phase	–	1%	Q_{in}
3	Single-phase	Graphite heating (uniform)	–	Q_{in}
4	Single-phase	Salt heating (uniform)	–	Q_{in}
5	Single-phase	Salt + Graphite heating (non-uniform)	–	Q_{in}
6	Two-phase	Graphite heating (uniform)	1%	Q_{in}
7	Two-phase	Salt heating (uniform)	1%	Q_{in}
8	Two-phase	Salt + Graphite heating (non-uniform)	1%	Q_{in}
9	Single-phase	Graphite heating (uniform)	–	$2.75 \times Q_{in}$
10	Single-phase	Graphite heating (uniform)	–	$3.25 \times Q_{in}$
11	Single-phase	Graphite heating (uniform)	–	$4.50 \times Q_{in}$
12	Two-phase	Graphite heating (uniform)	1%	$2.75 \times Q_{in}$
13	Two-phase	Graphite heating (uniform)	1%	$3.25 \times Q_{in}$
14	Two-phase	Graphite heating (uniform)	1%	$4.50 \times Q_{in}$

2.2. SAM Setup for Code-to-Code Comparison

SAM is a one-dimensional finite-element code used to generate reference solutions for this benchmark. CHT is modeled by coupling the one-dimensional channel to a two-dimensional axisymmetric solid domain representing the surrounding graphite moderator. The MSRE stadium channel is represented using an equivalent circular mapping that preserves the hydraulic diameter D_h , flow area A_c , wetted perimeter P_w , and total graphite volume. The outer graphite boundaries are adiabatic (homogeneous Neumann condition) and the inlet channel boundary condition specifies the mass flow rate derived from the fluid density and volumetric flow rate ($\dot{m} = \rho \cdot Q_{in}$).

The forced-flow single-channel heating cases (Cases 3–5) are used for direct comparison with SyTH and are simulated using the pure FLiBe properties. The cases are solved at steady state using a Pre-conditioned Jacobian-Free Newton–Krylov (PJFNK) method with an LU preconditioner. The channel is discretized with 80 axial elements and the graphite wall with two radial elements, using second-order shape functions for the primary variables. To ensure a consistent basis for comparison, both codes assume fully developed laminar heat transfer using the Sellars *et al.* [18] correlation ($Nu = 4.36$), apply the laminar Darcy friction factor ($Re < 2300$) for wall friction, and neglect minor-loss (K -factor) contributions at the inlet and outlet.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Results from the SyTH simulations for the progression cases listed in Table II are presented in this section. The discussion begins with a code-to-code benchmark against SAM for the single-phase forced-heating cases (Cases 3–5). A mesh refinement study was performed in SyTH using the SAM solution as the reference, and the axial mesh was progressively refined until the SyTH axial temperature profile converged.

Figure 2 summarizes the axial discretizations considered for each case and the converged SyTH–SAM temperature comparisons.

Figure 2. Benchmark for the single-phase forced-heating cases (Cases 3–5). Top row: mesh refinement and convergence. Bottom row: SyTH–SAM axial salt temperature profiles and temperature differences.

At the converged mesh resolution, the maximum absolute temperature difference between SyTH and SAM was 0.62 K. The largest discrepancy occurs in Case 5 with axially non-uniform heating. This may be due to the differences in the CHT geometry. SAM solves CHT in a one-dimensional/two-dimensional axisymmetric cylindrical geometry, whereas SyTH applies CHT to a three-dimensional cuboid mesh in the graphite region. These differing geometric conditions can alter heat spreading under adiabatic outer-wall conditions, leading to shifts in axial temperature distribution. Overall, the

agreement observed for Cases 3–5 supports the use of the converged SyTH mesh for the remaining progression suite.

Next, results are presented using the converged SyTH mesh and focus on two case-to-case studies: (i) volumetric flow-rate variation under uniform graphite heating (Cases 9–11) and (ii) changes in salt composition for the non-uniform heating case (Case 5). Figure 3 compares axial salt temperature profiles for the flow-rate variation cases (left) and the changes between pure FLiBe and MSRE fuel salt (right).

Figure 3. Case-to-case comparison of axial salt temperature for increasing volumetric flow-rate (left) and salt composition and heat-transfer closure variation (right)

Both case-to-case comparisons in Figure 3 show good agreement with the SAM reference solution. As expected, increasing the volumetric flow rate decreases the salt outlet temperature by 2.2 K, while in Case 5 switching between pure-salt and fuel-salt thermophysical-property correlations shifts the outlet temperature by 1.9 K. In contrast, the two-phase flow cases with a prescribed 1% inlet void fraction (Cases 6–8 and 12–14) produced negligible changes in the steady-state axial temperature relative to their corresponding single-phase cases from both SAM and SyTH. While the void fraction effects are weak in these steady-state single-channel thermal calculations, they are expected to become more prominent in coupled multiphysics settings, particularly when void-dependent neutronics and reactivity feedback are included. Overall, these progression problems establish a steady-state single-channel baseline for SyTH and motivate extensions to transient conditions, multichannel configurations, and high-fidelity CFD comparisons.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrated a progression-style thermal-hydraulic benchmark using SyTH through a series of single-channel cases with conjugate heat transfer between the salt and graphite. A mesh-convergence study was performed, and a comparison between the converged SyTH solutions and SAM for Cases 3–5 and Cases 9–11 showed suitable agreement in the salt temperature distributions within 0.62 K. The results show that increasing flow rate and changing the salt composition decrease the outlet temperature by 2.2 K and 1.9 K, respectively, while 1% void fraction produced negligible results from both SAM and SyTH. Collectively, these progression problems, spanning uniform and non-uniform heat sources, salt property variations, flow-rate changes, and void introduction, provide a structured approach for benchmarking single-channel thermal-hydraulic behavior using SyTH. Future work will extend these cases to higher-fidelity and coupled simulations following a similar progression:

- (1) **Transient single-channel simulations:** The single-channel cases will be extended to include transient conditions to investigate pump start-up and coast-down behavior. These transients will provide a foundation for evaluating the dynamic response of the drift-flux model.
- (2) **Multichannel steady-state and transient configurations:** The same progression of boundary and heat transfer conditions will be applied to multichannel reactor geometries under both steady-state and transient operation. This will enable assessment of inter-channel coupling effects, flow redistribution, and graphite heat transfer behavior.
- (3) **High-fidelity CFD simulations:** High-fidelity CFD simulations of the single-channel will be conducted to serve as another code-to-code comparison suite using foamForNuclear [19].
- (4) **Multiphysics coupling with neutronics solvers:** The final phase will focus on coupling the SyTH module with a high-fidelity neutron transport solver, such as MPACT, to enable fully integrated multiphysics simulations [20]. This will allow for understanding of the coupled neutronic-thermal-hydraulic feedback, salt-gas interaction, and reactivity behavior.

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